

European Sustainable
Mining & Innovation
Network (ESMIN)

Policy Brief

Leveraging Earth Observation and Machine Learning to
Address Critical Raw Material Challenges in the EU

March 2026

This policy brief was compiled by MultiMiner, with inputs from GoldenRAM, MOSMIN, AGEMERA, M4Mining, and MINEYE. All participating projects are funded by the European Union. Views expressed in this policy brief are not the views of the European Union or funding organisations.

Introduction

Critical raw materials (CRMs) are central to Europe's economy and its transition to a sustainable and digital future. They are essential for the development of advanced technologies for clean energy and digital infrastructures. For instance, lithium, cobalt and nickel are used in batteries for electric vehicles, Rare Earth Elements (REE) are critical for permanent magnets in wind turbines and electronics, and copper, silicon and tantalum are required for artificial intelligence (AI) infrastructures. Demand for these materials is predicted to increase manifold over the next decades, while recent crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic and geopolitical tensions have shown how fragile and import-dependent Europe's supply chains remain.

Securing reliable access to CRMs is now a strategic priority, and the European Commission has introduced the European Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA), as part of its Green Deal Industrial Plan. The CRMA sets ambitious goals: scale up domestic production, diversify sourcing, increase circularity (recycling and substitution), and strengthen permitting, monitoring and innovation. Achieving these objectives requires not only funding and regulatory reform but also robust, operational technologies capable of improving CRM exploration, mining operations, environmental monitoring, traceability and regulatory compliance across the full CRM lifecycle.

Earth Observation (EO) and Machine Learning (ML) feature among the most promising fields to address these objectives. EO provides a continuous flow of information on geology, the environment, land use and ground stability while ML helps turning complex datasets into practical insights. Together, they can reduce costs and risks in mineral exploration, increase the sustainability and efficiency of mining operations, improve environmental monitoring, and speed up decision-making. Several Horizon Europe projects, joining forces within the European Sustainable Mining and Innovation Network (ESMIN), are developing and testing such innovative EO and ML solutions. This policy brief presents preliminary results and illustrates how EO and ML can support mining companies, geological surveys, non-governmental organisations and national institutions in delivering on the CRMA objectives.

Earth Observation and Machine Learning Innovations

The CRMA sets targets for 2030 for the domestic production of CRM: extract at least 10%, process at least 40%, and recycle at least 25% of the EU's annual consumption of critical raw materials. In addition, the CRMA aims to limit the share of any single third-country supplier to no more than 65% of the EU's annual consumption of a given critical raw material. In parallel the CRMA will enforce environmental protection by improving circularity and sustainability of critical raw materials, and in particular by improving the retrieval of critical raw materials from extractive waste in current mining activities but also from historical mining waste sites.

The following projects funded under the Horizon Europe funding programme provided EO and ML innovations to support the CRM exploration, sustainable mining operations, circular mining (including waste valorisation) and environmental protection objectives of the CRMA.

MultiMiner

- **Mineral Mapper:** advanced mapping algorithms using artificial intelligence and machine learning approaches to automatically identify and map minerals from satellite and airborne data. They improve accuracy of mineral mapping for a variety of CRM deposit types, increasing the efficiency of exploration.
- **Dedicated CRM Spectral Library:** specialised database of spectral characteristics of minerals built based on field and laboratory measurements and AI-generated synthetic data. Each entry includes detailed mineralogical and chemical information, supporting more precise detection and identification of critical minerals.
- **Mineral Prospectivity Wizard:** a decision-support tool that translates complex Earth Observation data into prospectivity maps for exploration geologists. It helps prioritise areas with high potential for CRM deposits, streamlining exploration planning and reducing fieldwork.
- **Generic Mine Site Monitoring (GMSM):** a novel and flexible framework that continuously monitors mine sites combining data from satellites and drones with a limited number of in-situ data. By combining multiple data sources at different temporal and spectral resolutions, it supports environmentally sustainable mining practices.
- **Safety Monitoring:** a suite of dedicated algorithms monitoring mining tailing storage compositions, dam and open pit stability, allowing for valorisation of tailings and safer mining operations.
- **Specialised Environment Monitoring:** a suite of specialised algorithms tracking water quality and acid mine drainage, plant diversity, ground moisture and dust dispersion enabling early detection of environmental hazards.

GoldenRAM

- **GoldenRAM platform:** a cloud-based Earth Observation and AI system designed to support Europe's Critical Raw Materials sector across the entire mining lifecycle—from mineral exploration to post-closure environmental monitoring. It integrates multi-source geospatial data with advanced AI analytics to deliver actionable insights for mining companies, regulators, researchers, and investors, promoting responsible and sustainable mining aligned with EU goals.
- **AI Knowledge Packs (AIKP):** modular, domain-specific AI components that combine machine learning models, geospatial analytics, and mining expertise to deliver targeted insights across the raw materials value chain. They are designed to accelerate decision-making by providing ready-to-use predictive tools for exploration, extraction, and environmental monitoring within the platform.
- **Creating a database of Mapping CRMMR occurrences of Ukraine:** The GoldenRAM project's work in Ukraine is focused on integrating existing Ukrainian raw materials databases and creating a mirrored version within the project's data infrastructure. The work related to Ukraine focuses on mapping potential critical raw material (CRM) occurrences using advanced geospatial and AI-driven techniques. This includes integrating geological datasets, satellite

- imagery, and mineral prospectivity models to identify high-priority exploration zones, supporting sustainable resource development and aligning with EU strategic autonomy goals.
- **AI-Driven Mineral Prospectivity:** Advanced machine learning models combined with geospatial data to predict critical raw material (CRM) occurrences with high accuracy.
- **Tools to support Safety Monitoring and Risk Assessment:** GoldenRAM uses AI-driven geospatial analytics and predictive modelling to identify early indicators of environmental risks to ensure safe operations in operational and post-closure phases geohazards, monitor environmental risks, and ensure safe mining operations in operational and post-closure phases.
- **Circular mining tools:** Integrated lifecycle analysis and sustainability metrics to promote resource efficiency and recycling of CRMs.
- **Environmental Monitoring & Compliance:** Automated tools for tracking post-mining impacts and ensuring alignment with EU sustainability and strategic autonomy goals.

MOSMIN

- **Integrated geotechnical monitoring of tailing dams:** Near real-time surface-subsurface displacement anomaly detection and stability assessment to detect early signs of structural instability in tailings dams and guide targeted mitigation, reinforcement, or drainage measures.
- **Monitoring of contaminant source and pathways:** Time-resolved contaminant potential and severity maps identifying emission sources, transport pathways, and attenuation zones to support optimisation of waste deposition, additive dosing, and prioritisation of mitigation actions.
- **Rehabilitation and impact monitoring:** Time-series maps of vegetation health, diversity, and structure to monitor degradation linked to mining expansion or pollution, and to evaluate the success of rehabilitation and erosion-control efforts.
- **Assessment of valorisation potential:** Integrated 3D mineralogical and geophysical models delineating secondary resource domains and quantifying waste geometry to support resource inventorying and guide reprocessing/reuse strategies.

AGEMERA

- **Non-invasive Exploration Suite:** Integration of drone-based geophysics (magnetics, radiometrics, passive seismics) and muography with AI-driven data fusion for 3D geological modelling and anomaly detection.
- **AGEMERA GUI: AI Data Fusion Platform:** A machine learning framework that combines EO, geological, and geophysical datasets in 3D to improve mineral prospectivity mapping and reduce exploration uncertainty.
- **Local Perception and Social Acceptance Analytics:** Application to analyse citizen perception and social acceptance data, integrating it with environmental and spatial indicators to support transparent and responsible exploration planning.
- **Sustainability-linked Decision Support:** EO and ML methods linked with sustainability indicators (biodiversity, land use, emissions) to inform environmentally responsible exploration.

M4Mining

- **Real-Time UAV Hyperspectral Mapping (BIFROST) and Automated Processing Chain (INTACOR, BREEZE):** An integrated and automated processing workflow that produces reflectance maps and mineral classifications in real time. This significantly accelerates data delivery, enabling rapid ore–waste differentiation, tailings assessment and environmental hotspot detection and shows potential for applications outside of mining, such as: Emergency Response & Civil Protection, Military & Security Applications and Coastal and Glacier Monitoring.
- **Real-Time 3D Meshing, Data Fusion, and Visualisation Tools:** A framework that generates dense 3D meshes from LiDAR and optical data in real time and fuses them with hyperspectral or thermal layers. It supports immediate terrain assessment, slope monitoring and visual analysis for safer and more efficient mine-site operations.
- **Autonomous UAV Path Planning & Surface-Adaptive Inspection:** A flight-planning method that automatically adapts to changing pit geometries using real-time LiDAR data, ensuring efficient data capture in complex or hazardous mining environments.
- **Multi-Sensor Data Integration and User-Friendly Analytics Software:** Tools that integrate hyperspectral, LiDAR and optical data into accessible workflows for mineral mapping and site monitoring. User-friendly software lowers technical barriers and accelerates operational adoption of EO-based monitoring.
- **Mapping Framework for Mine Waste (Cyprus, Greece, Queensland):** Demonstrated use of multi-scale EO data, including EnMAP hyperspectral imagery, to map mine waste composition, identify environmental risks and support circularity assessments across diverse mining regions.
- **UAV-HSI Field Operations & Regulatory Guidance:** A best-practice framework for deploying UAV hyperspectral systems at mine sites, covering calibration, flight operations and regulatory compliance. It supports safe, harmonised adoption of UAV-based EO technologies in the mining sector.

MINEYE

- **IPOP (Interfacing, Programming and Optimization Platform)** and related algorithms and plug-ins, a cloud web interface and API to enable fusion of multi-source Earth Observation (Copernicus, commercial satellites, hyperspectral missions), airborne/drone and in-situ data with machine learning and geostatistics to support exploration, operational monitoring, tailings assessment and closure planning. The IPOP core components are described as follows:
- **Mineral Prospectivity Maps (MPM):** machine-learning-based tool for improved prospectivity mapping in mineralization zones at both regional and local scales by fusing EO data (optical, SAR, hyperspectral) with exploration data (geophysical, geochemical) and geological data. The tool is trained on known deposits and geological parameters and helps identify areas of high potential for mineral occurrences including CRMs.
- **LiquidEarth EO plugin:** cloud-based 3D visualization and structural modelling environment that integrates EO-derived layers and geological models into an immersive scene. It enables users to visualize mineral prospectivity, geological structures, pits, residues and associated

- uncertainties in three dimensions, leveraging probabilistic geomodelling and real-time interaction. It makes complex EO and modelling outputs understandable for both technical and non-technical stakeholders and supports transparent review of exploration, planning and risk scenarios.
- **Inventory Map & Mining Residues Package (IM-MRP)**: combines a country-scale inventory map of mining residues with detailed local analytical packages. At national scale, it maps and classifies tailings, waste rock and stockpiles using EO data, existing databases and ancillary data. At site scale, it delivers 3D tailings models, algorithms and time-series tools for monitoring environmental indicators and stability, and for assessing re-mining potential. This provides a replicable workflow for digital tailings registries, prioritisation of remediation and circular re-mining opportunities.
- **Global Stability Assessment (GSA)**: provides an integrated assessment of ground and structural stability at active and abandoned mines by combining satellite SAR interferometry, drone-based GPR and photogrammetry, in-situ geotechnical measurements and numerical modelling. It generates time-series deformation maps, factors-of-safety estimates and stability classifications for pits, slopes and tailings facilities at the demo sites, providing safety indicators. This multi-sensor, model-driven approach enables early detection of instability, supports compliance with safety regulations and strengthens regulatory oversight of mining and residue infrastructures.
- **Three demonstration sites covering diverse contexts and materials**: Tharsis Mining / Iberian Pyrite Belt (Spain), Norrbotten ore province (Sweden), and underground chromite mine (Albania). These span greenfield, brownfield, tailings and full life-cycle cases to validate utility and replicability.

EO & ML Innovations	CRM Exploration	Mining Operations	Circular Mining	Environmental Protection
MultiMiner				
Mineral Mapper	X	X		
Dedicated CRM Spectral Library	X	X	X	
Mineral Prospectivity Wizard	X			
Generic Mine Site Monitoring		X		X
Safety Monitoring		X	X	
Specialised Environment Monitoring		X		X
MOSMIN				
Integrated geotechnical monitoring of tailing dams		X		X
Monitoring of contaminant source and pathways		X		X
Rehabilitation and impact monitoring				X
Assessment of valorisation potential	X		X	

GoldenRAM				
GoldenRAM Platform	X	X	X	X
AI Knowledge Packs (AIKP)	X	X	X	X
Mapping CMR occurrences of Ukraine	X			
AI-Driven Mineral Prospectivity	X			
Safety Monitoring and Risk Identification		X		
Circular Mining Tools			X	
Environmental Monitoring & Compliance				X
AGEMERA				
Non-invasive Exploration Suite	X			
AGEMERA GUI: AI Data Fusion Platform	X			
Local Perception and Social Acceptance Analytics				X
Sustainability-linked Decision Support				X
M4Mining				
Real-Time UAV Hyperspectral Mapping (BIFROST) and		X		X
Real-Time 3D Meshing and Data Fusion Framework and		X		X
Autonomous UAV Path Planning & Surface-Adaptive		X		
Multi-Sensor Data Integration and User-Friendly Analytics	X	X	X	X
Mapping Framework for Mine Waste in the Republic of			X	X
UAV-HSI Field Operations & Regulatory Guidance		X	X	X
MINEYE				
IPOP platform	X	X	X	X
Mineral Prospectivity Maps (MPM)	X	X		
LiquidEarth EO plugin	X	X	X	
Inventory Map & Mining Residues Package (IM-MRP)		X	X	X
Global Stability Assessment (GSA)		X		X

Challenges to Adaption

Limited Awareness on EO capabilities and Knowledge Transfer

The rapid advancement of EO and ML technologies is not matched by sufficient stakeholder awareness or understanding of their operational benefits. Weak dissemination channels and limited mechanisms for knowledge exchange hinder the translation of research outputs into practical applications across the mining sector in Europe. Recent findings from Horizon Europe initiatives confirm that the barriers to adoption are often institutional rather than technological. Although tools such as InSAR, LiDAR, UAV imaging, and AI-based data fusion are technically mature, their uptake is constrained by limited institutional capacity, fragmented data governance, and regulatory misalignment. Most national frameworks still rely on field inspections and do not formally recognise EO- or ML-derived evidence. Moreover, many authorities and operators lack the expertise to interpret EO and ML data, depending on external consultants instead of building internal capacity.

EO data analysis and ML still requires extensive in situ reference data

EO-based analysis continues to rely on in-situ reference data, particularly for training and validating ML models. However, it can provide continuous monitoring for changes and pinpoint locations for further investigations. Statistically sound accuracy assessment of spatiotemporal maps relies on extensive ground data, ideally distributed randomly in space and time, or continuous data from permanent monitoring stations. These constraints of remote sensing are not always compatible with the operational limitations of active mine sites. Furthermore, EO cannot replace in-situ measurements, only complement them. Within Horizon Europe projects, it has also become evident that data interoperability across EO, geophysics, and perception datasets remains limited. The integration of these heterogeneous data sources requires common standards and interoperable formats to enable reliable model calibration and validation. The solution to this challenge is in the use of the specialised data processing and AI analytics platforms, such as those developed in GoldenRAM and AGEMERA projects.

High Cost and Accessibility of Earth Observation Data

High-quality commercial EO datasets remain prohibitively expensive for many potential users, especially when high spatial resolution or frequent temporal coverage is required. Without coordinated policy mechanisms that improve affordability, promote open-access data use, and encourage the integration of commercial and open datasets, the uptake of EO-based solutions will remain limited. For new acquisitions, quotas for research are often too small (particularly for VHR imagery and SAR), and scheduling acquisitions for specific sensors can be difficult (e.g. WorldView-3). Uneven access to high-resolution, analysis-ready datasets across Europe further reinforces existing disparities between research institutions, regulatory bodies, and industry actors. However, developments in drone-based sensing technologies have opened up completely new avenues for mine site monitoring. As know-how and access to drone-based hyperspectral and SAR technologies is still limited, availability of EU based data acquisition, data processing and

interpretation services have to improve in the mining industry for them to benefit from these developments. Potential solution here might be the stronger commercial leverage of the popular data processing platforms from the established players in the market; however, the legal and commercial aspects of this approach are still being explored in the GoldenRAM project.

Regulatory fragmentation for UAV-based EO in mining

Fragmented national regulations on UAV flight permissions, safety protocols and airspace management slows the deployment of UAV hyperspectral systems, increases administrative burden, and limits cross-border operational scaling. Some regions have community or workforce concerns about UAV operations, especially regarding privacy, safety and perceived surveillance. These issues require engagement strategies and transparency, which are not yet systematically implemented.

In addition, permitting and reporting frameworks in some jurisdictions are written around traditional methods (drilling, ground surveys, in-situ sensors). If EO-based evidence is not formally recognised, companies have less incentive to invest in it.

Reliability and Interpretability of Models

Interpreting multispectral, hyperspectral or SAR data, and running ML models, requires skills that many mining companies (especially smaller ones) do not have in-house. Previous experiences with underperforming, proprietary, or poorly validated models have fostered scepticism amongst the potential end users. In the absence of Europe-wide standards for data quality, security, model validation, and transparency, stakeholders remain cautious and risk-averse towards the adoption of new EO and ML-based technologies. Trust in automated analytics also remains low due to limited training, transparency and the lack of certification and harmonised validation mechanisms. Clear quality assurance frameworks and model auditability would significantly improve user confidence.

Data quality, resolution, standards and coverage limits

In some regions, cloud cover, snow cover, vegetation, or lack of high-resolution data reduce the reliability of EO-based products, especially for early-stage exploration or detailed operational monitoring. Without agreed standards for EO-based prospectivity, tailings monitoring or stability assessment (e.g. minimum resolution, update frequency, validation requirements), regulators and companies may doubt the legal robustness of decisions based on EO.

Structural Barriers to Innovation

The mining sector remains conservative and risk-averse, with innovation often constrained by rigid operational frameworks and short-term economic priorities. Geopolitical instability, commodity price fluctuations, and evolving regulatory requirements further amplify uncertainty, discouraging long-term investment in EO and ML innovations. New EO-based approaches are often seen as “experimental” until long-term evidence is available.

Although the technical readiness of integrated EO–geophysics–ML pipelines is high, operational and social integration continue to lag. Despite high technical readiness, EO outputs are not yet formally accepted as evidence in mine permitting, environmental monitoring or closure inspections. Lack of regulatory recognition prevents operators and authorities from fully leveraging existing data capabilities. Many organisations lack the computational infrastructure to validate, store and integrate these data in operational decision-making. UAV-based data acquisition still faces complex licensing and regulatory constraints, and public understanding of ML-supported exploration is limited. Building social acceptance on the usage of ML methods requires transparent communication and ethical data handling. Harmonised EU guidance on non-invasive exploration standards and ML ethics would accelerate responsible technology adoption across the mineral sector.

Recommendations

Empirical evidence by the Horizon Europe projects demonstrates that machine-learning (ML) and Earth Observation (EO) technologies are technically mature but remain underused due to limited availability of the services, fragmented regulations, limited capacity of end-users to adopt them, and uneven recognition of digital data in environmental governance. To advance the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA) and the Green Deal Industrial Plan, EU and national frameworks should formally recognise EO- and ML-derived datasets in permitting, mine-closure, and post-mining monitoring. Regulatory sandboxes, harmonised data and metadata standards, and shared validation protocols would build trust and legal certainty. Embedding EO/ML skills in higher education and professional training, alongside co-funded demonstration projects, open-access infrastructures (e.g., Copernicus Data Space, CREODIAS), cross-sector data integration platforms, and partnerships, can accelerate uptake. Integrating these measures into CRMA implementation will help mainstream digital monitoring and exploration as a foundation for sustainable, transparent, and resilient raw-material value chains across Europe.

Limited Awareness on EO capabilities and Knowledge Transfer

- Establish targeted training and knowledge exchange programmes for industry professionals, regulators, and researchers to demonstrate EO and ML capabilities in operational contexts.
- Centralise knowledge under EU or national coordination to curate best practices and methodologies, for EO/ML innovations.
- Continued support to demonstration and pilot projects that provide evidence of economic, environmental, and social benefits of EO/ML applications.
- Incentivise academia–industry collaboration through dedicated funding calls and innovation networks that foster long-term partnerships.
- Recognise non-invasive EO–geophysics–ML approaches as valid evidence within CRMA-aligned exploration, permitting, and environmental monitoring frameworks.

- Combine EO with on-the-ground verification, provide model uncertainty visualization: display uncertainty volumes and confidence intervals (e.g. where data are sparse or modelled), avoiding a false sense of precision and supporting more cautious decisions where needed.
- Promote integration of local perception and social acceptance insights into EO/ML-based decision systems to ensure responsible and transparent exploration.
- Establish EU “living labs” at representative mine sites where UAV-based hyperspectral and 3D monitoring workflows can be tested jointly by industry, SMEs, regulators and geological surveys, accelerating TRL-to-deployment transition, streamlining access to sites for prototyping and testing.
- Use EO-based mapping to identify secondary raw materials, evaluate re-mining potential and prioritise waste valorisation. Incorporate these EO tools explicitly into circular mining action plans under the CRMA.
- Develop EO-specific technical guidelines and standards (co-created with industry, regulators and EO experts) to define minimum requirements for EO products (resolution, revisit, accuracy, validation) and protocols for EO-based tailings monitoring, prospectivity mapping and stability assessment. Align these with international frameworks (e.g. ICMM tailings standards).
- Offer regulators and stakeholders an intuitive interface/way to review exploration plans, environmental risks and land-use conflicts.

EO data analysis requires in-situ reference data

- Encourage the adoption of EO and ML technologies in specific cases where comparable accuracy to in-situ data can be achieved, such as drone-based LiDAR and photogrammetric imaging for generating digital elevation models and monitoring volumetric changes.
- Utilise unsupervised ML techniques, which do not require training data, to monitor changes and to enhance the planning and operational efficiency of fieldwork activities.
- Prioritise EO/ML approaches that perform well with limited training data, including weakly supervised and self-supervised methods, and EO foundation models, combined with fine-tuning or transfer learning. In most cases, EO/ML outputs are less accurate and precise than in-situ observations but still provide a spatially mapping dimension that field data typically lack.
- Ensure statistically robust accuracy assessment, employing representative in-situ reference data, optimising the use of limited datasets, and reporting confidence intervals for all estimates (e.g. MultiMiner thematic accuracy assessment procedures).
- Promote sharing of high-quality in-situ reference data in open access from mine sites to support EO-based ML model development and transfer. To this end, MultiMiner will publish a field guidebook describing protocols and good practices for field work data collection and standardized in-situ metadata documentation.
- Support cross-sector data integration platforms combining EO data with subsurface (geophysical, muography, passive seismic) and social datasets for holistic critical raw materials (CRM) assessments.

High Cost and Limited Accessibility of EO Data

- Promote open-access and public–private data partnerships to increase availability of EO datasets with high spatial and temporal resolutions
- Foster and further develop co-financing schemes or data acquisition grants for research and demonstration projects to lower entry barriers for SMEs and non-for-profit entities, such as the ESA Third-Party Missions (TPM), the Copernicus Contributing Mission (CCM) and mission specific mechanisms (e.g. Planet Research or Student quotas).
- Mandate data interoperability and standardisation across platforms to enable seamless integration of open and commercial datasets.
- Encourage reuse of existing EO data assets through national and European data repositories (such as the [CDSE Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem](#) and the [CREODIAS EO data collection](#)) to maximise efficiency and reduce duplication.

Data Security and Technological Risk

- Develop European standards for EO data harmonisation and ML model transparency, security, and ethical governance.
- Support regulatory sandboxes or testbed frameworks allowing controlled experimentation with new EO and ML technologies under reduced compliance risk.
- Foster cross-sector data governance frameworks to ensure secure handling of sensitive mining data and build stakeholder trust in EO/ML solutions.
- Ensure ML transparency and ethical data governance to foster trust among citizens, regulators, and the mining industry.

Structural Barriers to Innovation

- Integrate digital innovation objectives (including EO and ML adoption) into national mining, environmental, and raw materials strategies.
- Encourage multi-stakeholder co-development between technology providers, end-users, and regulators to ensure solutions align with operational and policy needs.
- Promote EO/ML innovations and capacity building training within the mining sector to reduce inertia and facilitate integration of digital solutions.

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More Information

- MultiMiner: www.multiminer.eu
- GoldenRAM: www.goldenram-project.eu
- MOSMIN: www.mosmin.eu
- AGEMERA: www.agemera.eu
- M4Mining: www.m4mining.eu
- MINEYE: <https://mineye-project.eu>

Citation

10.5281/zenodo.18610989

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- [IEA \(2021\), The Role of Critical Minerals in Clean Energy Transitions](#)
- [EUSPA Earth Day 2023: Uncovering Europe's much needed critical raw materials from space.](#)
- [European Commission CRM list 2023](#)

Funding

MultiMiner was funded by the European Union's HORIZON research and innovation actions programme under Grant Agreement No. 101091374.

GoldenRAM was funded by the European Union's HORIZON research and innovation actions programme under Grant Agreement No. 101138153.

AGEMERA was funded by the European Union's HORIZON research and innovation actions programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058178.

MOSMIN is funded by the European Union Agency for the Space Programme and the European Union's Horizon Europe innovation action programme under grant agreement No 101131740.

M4Mining was funded by the European Union's HORIZON research and innovation actions programme under Grant Agreement No. 101091462

MINEYE was funded by the European Union's HORIZON research and innovation actions programme under Grant Agreement No. 101138456.

